

Event metadata

Event title	WORKSHOP: Phylogenetics: back to basics
Event type	Workshop
Date of event	1 July 2024
Time of event	11am - 3pm AEST
Topic description	<p>Phylogenetics is essential for comparing biological species and understanding biodiversity for conservation. This workshop discusses the basic principles and methods of phylogenetic inference and what you can learn from phylogenetic estimation. It is intended to help you make informed decisions about which methods to use in your research.</p> <p>Using real-life data and standard tools that are (mostly) available in Galaxy, the workshop demonstrates the principles behind a variety of methods used to estimate phylogenetic trees from aligned sequence data or distance data.</p> <p>This is not a "how to" workshop, but is instead aimed at giving you a better understanding of the principles of phylogenetics and how the methods work. Maybe you've even built phylogenetic trees before but want to know more about the principles behind the tools.</p>
Format description	<p>Workshop, online via Zoom.</p> <p>Professor Michael Charleston led the training by introducing and demonstrating theoretical concepts in phylogenetics. The workshop made use of Galaxy Australia and SplitsTree4 to enable exploration of the output of common phylogenetics tools.</p> <p>A breakdown of timings and topics is provided in the schedule.</p> <p>Participation was free but subject to application with selection.</p> <p>Applications were reviewed by the organising committee.</p> <p>Number of participants = 27</p>
Identifier(s)/URL	https://www.biocommons.org.au/events/phylogenetics-2024
Licence	Materials are shared under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International agreement unless otherwise stated on the materials
Keywords	<p>Bioinformatics http://edamontology.org/topic_0091</p> <p>Analysis http://edamontology.org/operation_2945</p> <p>Phylogenetics http://edamontology.org/topic_3293</p>
Contact	training@biocommons.org.au

Audience	This workshop was for Australian molecular biologists who want to know more about phylogenetic trees.
Prerequisites	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> You should know how molecular sequence data is produced and what it looks like. Some familiarity with using Galaxy is assumed. If you are new to Galaxy you will need to register for a free Galaxy Australia account. We recommend watching this brief introduction to Galaxy Australia and working through the Galaxy Basics for Everyone tutorial before joining the workshop. No coding experience is required.
Technical requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Zoom chat was used to facilitate discussions. Access to the internet, speakers, a webcam, microphone and Zoom. The workshop used Galaxy Australia to provide access to commonly used phylogenetics tools. Access was facilitated via the Galaxy Australia Training Infrastructure as a Service (TlaaS) Participants were required to download and install SplitsTree4 to visualise phylogenetic networks.
Learning outcomes	<p>By the end of the workshop you should be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe the basic concepts behind phylogenetic trees and how they are made Read and interrogate a phylogeny encountered in the literature Use standard tools to align a set of molecular sequences Assess the quality of a molecular sequence alignment and be able to modify it appropriately for phylogenetic analysis Use standard tools to estimate a phylogenetic tree based on a set of aligned molecular sequences Assess the reliability of estimated phylogenies with bootstrapping Explore phylogenetic signal using phylogenetic networks <p>We will not cover:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Workflows from read data to sequences How to get an alignment (much: will use automated methods) Bayesian phylogenetics: MCMC / BEAST / MrBayes
Lead Trainers	Professor Michael Charleston, University of Tasmania
Facilitators	Michael Thang, Queensland Cyber Infrastructure Foundation and Galaxy Australia.
Training materials	<p>The training materials from this workshop are available on the Galaxy Training Network:</p> <p>https://training.galaxyproject.org/training-material/topics/evolution/tutorials/abc_intro_phylo/tutorial.html</p>